

Brian Paul Kaess Diary: 2022 to 2024
by Brian Paul Kaess
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Another quiet Saturday in Durango

Date 28-05-2022

(1 of 20 Diary Entries)

Today, Mayte (Mayte Urbina Kaess) went to Babysit and work on her Construction business in Durango, Mexico. Currently she is building a couple of houses in the Nogales area. There have been some thefts of construction equipment from her sites so she has brought some of the stuff home to keep in our house in Las Villas. She had us carry in bricks to the backyard to build a new chimney/oven for BBQ-ing carne azada. Mayte has made a number of improvements to our house: glass stairwell, new paneling on the kitchen and bathroom sink, etc.

Under Mayte is her supervisor Junior and he has a crew of about 7 construction workers. We cruise into Durango alot from the south suburbs (near Sebastian Lerdo de Tejada) to shop at the supermarket and check in with Urbina family staying in Fracc. Lomas del Guadiana or the Barrio de Analco. We ate ham sandwichs today for dinner and I fed some cheese and ham to the cats as well as cat food/crackers. For breakfast, we ate scrambled eggs & mixed veggies on tortillas. Mayte likes to bring home gorditas on Saturday nights. We have three cats: Nana, Candy, and Nieve (Snow). a 4th Cat Nene died on Jan 5, 2022 after a few weeks of recovering from a mauling from the mean orange cat, a precocious neighborhood cat. My son Paul (Paul Jesus Kaess Urbina) has finished the Spring semester at Puebla (UDLAP) with a 95 average.

We have been living in Mexico now since December 2006, 17 ½ years. The Uvalde shooting has been all over the news in Durango on channel ten and Fore news. Channel 13 shows some nice quality Mexican cinema from the 1950's and 1960's.

Durango Gobernador (Govenor) and Durango Presidente Municipal (Mayor) elections are on June 5, 2022, I think. My favorite is Marina who is running for Gobenor for Morena party. Also decent is Gonzalo for PT who is running for Mayor. He has the most positive commercials. I have been tutoring our neighbor Valeria in English lessons. She is a nursing student at UJED and is the same age as Paul. Her Mother Cynthia is a police officer for the Durango state police (Policia Estatal). She also has a son Omar and two dogs Max and Coco. They like to wander over and chat with Mayte in the evenings. The Director of Health Services in Durango has declared the Pandemic over. I (Brian Paul Kaess) received the Aztra Zeneca booster in January 2022 and Mayte and Paul the same not long after. The Russians captured a key railway town in the Donbass. I hope the tide is not turning against the Ukrainians. They are causing alot of Russian casualties. But how long can they take it, artillery, rockets and all. I Believe Zelensky is a great Leader.

In the words of Giraldo, he is very `Churchillian.

Ramos Rumors

Date: 29-05-2022

(2 of 20 Diary Entries)

Probably the biggest Rumor in Ramos is the existence of the Ramos/San Carlos drug cartel. They reputedly have a large marijuana field in the vicinity of Ramos and Martinez, another nearby town. It is guarded by armed guards and children reputedly water the plants. The marijuana growers receive support from the Sinaloa and Colombian cartels who have installed night lights to keep the plants growing 24/7, Another Rumor is the existence of a 'golden bell' hidden in the walls of the local Catholic Church or Citadel. Some say a local man has found the bell and sold it off for money. Who knows? Some also say there are gold coins or doubloons hidden in the wells around Ramos, Lupe reputedly found one.

Coming and Going

DATE: 30-05-2022

(3 of 20 Diary Entries)

Lupe came from Ramos to Durango in early May 2022 to visit the family. She stayed with Dr. Juan Urbina, then left for Ramos, came back, and stayed with Judy Urbina. I did not get a chance to see her.

Mayte visited Mazatlan from May B-11, 2022, with her Mom and Judy and Mexican Family. Paul and I stayed in Las Villas. Mayte was in Mazatlan for Mother's Day. They stayed in the Royal Villas Mazatlan. Garret will visit us in Durango after Cancun in July 3-7, 2022. Lourdes Bustos, Maytes friend from Ecuador, may visit us in December. She lives in Champaign, Illinois. She used to live in Chicago.

We Visited Said Digna Health Clinic in Zona Centro in Durango
 Thursday, Feb. 9, 2023
 (4 of 20 Diary Entries)

This morning, we got up early to go for a set of lab tests that Dr. Arturo Flores ordered for me as a Diabetic patient. Mayte fixed me breakfast early- eggs and tomatos on tortillas with milk. When we got there, we noticed an old lady selling hot tamales right in front of the clinic. I think I paid 32 pesos for four moist, hot, tasty 'rojo' tamales. They went down smooth! We took a number, registered, and I got a urine and blood test. I believe Mayte picked up the results later that day. That's what I like about Mexican healthcare- inexpensive and efficient. Yesterday, Mayie said her family arrived from both Florida and Arizona. Her Nephews Jonathan and David Urbina Jr. came with their women Crystal and Gabriela, and David's son Rolando, to show Braulio his 1st Gr. Grandson. What a joy that was with two Mariachi Bands playing. There was also Super Bowl Sunday too. Mexico is always a great place to party.

Mayte and Family go to see the Eclipse
 Sunday, October 15, 2023
 (5 of 20 Diary Entries)

Written by Brian Paul Kaess. This is a continuation of a Diary I started a year or so ago.

The past week or so has been interesting. The state of Durango, where I live, was suffering from severe drought, but has seen a resilience of rain that lasted a number of days. The 'Vacas' or cows must be happy!

Yesterday, Mayte brought over Angelica, Regina, Valente, & Daniel. Marisol is away on a trip to El Paso. The group stayed downtown last night to watch the eclipse that was predicted to happen yesterday. I got to stay home with my cats: Nana, Candy, & Nieve. My son Paul is studying at University in Puebla, and they are even teaching him how to draw Tattoos. I thought that was interesting, having been in the Military. I don't have any tattoos myself, but appreciate the art. Paul is dating a girl named Rose. Her family owns a French-style Restaurant in Puebla. Just the other day, Mayte and I drove in Central Durango down the prettiest road I have seen yet in Durango- it was near the former Govenor's Hacienda. I noticed plenty of beautiful Sunflowers nearby.

We took care of Cynthia's pets when she was away in Gomez Palacio-. There are three dogs: Max, Coco, and Boni, all Chihuahua's I believe. There Is also a cat named Luna. Areceli's German Sheperd (Medina) bit me a couple of times while I took my daily walk, but she seems to be getting used to me. Mayte, Areceli & Cynthia all belong to the Neighborhood association and help with recycling and stuff like that. We all live on the same Privada in Las Villas- namely Venecia,

My Brother Garret and his Colombian girlfriend Kathy will visit us in December at xmas time. I am looking forward to seeing him. He is doing well in his career. He told me he recently visited Chicago from Indianapolis where he lives now. Fun stuff! He visited me here in Las Villas in 2020 and 2022. Well, that is all for now.

Gaza Conflict heating up
 Saturday, October 21, 2023
 (6 of 20 Diary Entries)

It has been terrible to read the news and hear of the deaths of 1400 Israeli's and kidnapping of 200 others by Hamas in Southern Israel, I have some sympathies for the Palestinians and their plight, but this was way beyond the pale. I made a blog post at *the Evanston Roundtable* online newspaper, showing gratitude for the two Americans who were recently released by Hamas. I think perhaps Israel should consider exchanging prisoners, even though this may not be their policy. This may be the only way to bring the kidnapped Israeli's home. All I know is, I still like Gal Gadot! Hal

Candy slept on my back last night- she can be very cute and possessive of me, but she is a wonderful, furry friend. Mayte has been storing Halloween candy in Paul's room since the beginning of the month, but she keeps it locked, so it's tough luck for me. She fixes me coffee daily now. I used to drink coffee a lot when I worked the night shift at Edgewater, but those working-class days are gone. Hai We have been watching *Como en Casa* on Canal 10 or channel 10) in the mornings in Durango. Mayte tells me that one of the hostesses or (Conductoras) named Male Bechelani is related to her former boss Areceli at Campanita Jardin in Lomas. She is her niece and she was Miss Durango 2016 back in the day. She dances pretty good.

I chatted with Paul on the phone this morning. He said his study workload is diminished. He said he was still seeing Rose. I also asked him if he was eating OK, and he said he was. I told him not to drink too much and to stay away from drugs. He was interested in getting paperwork squared away so he can work in the US. I got some serious help in Genealogy when I used a database called Virginia Chronicle to scour for Swartz/Gibboney family articles. I even found some Deeds elsewhere for some members of the family. Good stuff!

Osiris dies from a Work-related Accident
 October 24, 2023
 (7 of 20 Diary Entries)

Mayte's 1st Cousin Osiris died tragically yesterday from a work-related injury on a construction site in Durango City. It appeared he was on a ladder, when he fell backwards, hitting his head, causing a severe injury. They had a photo of him with a drape over his body. He had been married twice and left behind a total of five kids. He was only in his 30's or something. He is Dra. Susanna Martinez's brother as well. She would stop by with Juanito and her Mom Chole (Mayte's Aunt) and see us on Sundays when we lived in the Barrio Tierra Blanco. This happened yesterday and a segment on the accident appeared on Channel 10 Durango the next day, that captured the news. They are going to bury him in the Panteon Jardin, which Mayte says is for 'rich' people. She said his headstone was very expensive. I am saddened by this incident because he was a young man so full of life.

Trick or Treating a Little Early on Saturday Night before Halloween
 October 28, 2023
 (8 of 20 Diary Entries)

Mayte told me that her neighbors on the Las Villas Development were going to Trick or Treat on this Saturday Night, days before Halloween, just to make it safer for the kids and parents to walk together. Yesterday, on Friday, I noticed Mayte had Boxes and Boxes of Candy stored in Paul's room. All kinds of Lollipops, Chocolate Malt Sticks (the best), caramel, wrapped sour candies, and so on. She started setting up about 6PM with a table in front of the House with five trays of candies on them. She was dressed like a Witch with a Silver Cross- very tasteful. Regina was dressed like a Widow with a white skull mask, almost Viennese style. Valente just wore a cape as a Vampire. Daniel was here too. She had the front door decorated with a hanging black spider, and also a black skeleton hanging out front.

From a block away on Privada Venecia, I noticed a crowd, almost a mob, of people begin approaching in our direction. They were the parents and kids led by Mayte. Marisol was parked out front and I sat out front. When they arrived, Angelica and Regina handed out the Candy to each kid, making sure each got an equal share. Some of the kids had cute costumes like an electric yellow robot suit, or a glowing mask. Angelica snuck me one of the chocolate sticks, saying 'this is for you.' She didn't want me to tell Mayte. Valeria was beaming about her new baby and waved to me, showing me her newborn baby in the stroller.

In the evening, I was able to eat a meal of azado (red spicy pork) and rice that Mayte had garnered from Lerdo earlier in the day. I shared a little with the pets: Boni and Nieve. We were all happy campers!

Internet Service On and Off
 November 13, 2023
 (9 of 20 Diary Entries)

I have asked Mayte to help me apply for a Mexican Permanent Resident Card, but she says it is too expensive, and she is busy with real estate. Sometimes, like in 2020, I apply for a six month visa at the Migration Office in Ciudad Juarez, but that is only a temporary fix.

Lately, Mayte has been fixing me Cappucino once a day in the mornings. It goes down hot and sugary. Sometimes its the little things that count. In addition, She buys a lot of apples. Furthermore, sometimes I like to buy 'penguinos' or other snacks at a food stall near the Diabetic Clinic in the Zona Hospitales. Also, the rains have been steady the past few days, which is nice for the crops. It turned cold today, so I took my walk a little early to help warm up.

Our internet service has not been as reliable as Tel-Mex that we used to have, but at least we pay less. We pay a provider in nearby Sebastian Lerdo de Tejada a monthly internet fee- all we do is go to the L-S Mart in Lerdo and pay the store manager/clerk the fee. They don't have any food stores/tiendas in Las Villas where we live, so if we have to foot it, we are forced to walk to Lerdo to buy goods- a mile and a half away. But luckily, our 2010 Mitsubishi Outlander is working fine and we just cruise it. We sometimes buy gas near Club Campestre at the Pe-Mex station there.

Domingo Arrieta and Durango Blvd. are arteries/streets we use often as well as the road near the Feria. They don't even seem to have names for some of the streets we use in the south suburbs, but perhaps they are just not listed properly.

When we lived in Durango City, I enjoyed going to Parque Guadiana to buy some of the best carne asada tacos in town with wonderful lettuce, but, alas, no more!

In July, Paul's Cousin Regina flew to Mexico City to participate in a Mexican Folkloric Dance event with other Catholic high school students. They gave her an award or something. The family is nice about Mexican Pride.

Paul is still studying in Puebla and Mayte says he is very busy. As far as I know, he is still dating Rose. Her family supposedly owns a French-style restaurant in Puebla and Paul has been there a couple of times at least, once at her Grandfather's birthday party. Paul has said, 'She is my girlfriend.'

Mayte, Judy and Parents visit Mazatlan

March 5, 2024

(10 of 20 Diary Entries)

Mayte arrived back in Durango last night from her short trip to Mazatlan. Judy, Maria Luisa, Mayte & Braulio all stayed at the Hotel Quijote Inn in Mazatlan. Mayte said there were lots of 'Gringos' in Mazatlan, with many living there. Judy sold a number of Houses recently and even Mayte sold one as well. But I don't think it was her 'show' home at 230 Nogales in Durango, which she always shows, but never sells. We are always watering the nice plants there...

I took a brief jaunt yesterday into Sebastian Lerdo de Tejada, aka 'Lerdo', to buy some snacks, soup, and cat food. I was really moving, fast & light. We have 4 cats now, including Nana, Candy, Nieve, & the kitten Sabrina. Sabrina and Nieve love playing. Nieve had a suitor cat visit last night (he was back-and-white) who was very friendly and kept cooing/purring at the window before coming inside and mingling. He is a very nice cat. So I guess the cats had their vacation too!

Mayte also sent word that Paul won 2nd place in a Chess Tournament at his School, UDLAP. He went to a Party with his friends and Rose's Uncle. He said he had a lot of fun. I jest that I taught him everything he knows!

During March, Garret has been on a to the Far East visting Tokyo, Japan, and Shangha, China, as part of a business trip for Ei Lilly, Inc. He is traveling with a number of coworkers of Chinese descent. It has been beautiful and sunny in Durango tis March. This is one of my favorite times of year.

Pay Day!

March 6, 2024

(11 of 20 Diary Entries)

Today is payday so Chow for now, Mayle and I went shopping today in downtown Durango, not only by Madero but also by the Mercado Abastos El Refugio nearby. Mayte says our Neighbor Sally and her Family own their candy store there. We dropped off some Cardboard boxes there for some easy recycling money. I bought some Jalapeño Sabritas, a slab of Mennonite Cheese, Macaroni. Chinese food & Cordon Blau Chicken at Sorianas. It was candy bars for everyone at Al Supers.

So we had a nice time shopping, watering the plants in Nogales, and driving back safely to Las Villas.

Brian receives a Free AHSGR Membership

March 11, 2024

(12 of 20 Diary Entries)

This morning, I received an email from some folks in Lincoln, Nebraska, that said I had won a Free One-Year Membership to American Historical Society of Germans from Russia [AHSGR]. This was because I participated in their online chat during Rootstech 2024. I learned a lot about Tech stuff too, including Chat GPT and Box.com. This has helped me a little bit in my Genealogy. The AHSGR stuff is great because I have a read a little on the subject and suspect that maybe some of my collateral ancestors from Benningen may have migrated to the Volga or Black Sea Regions in search of greener grass, so to speak. Just have to figure out who they are? At this point, it is just a hunch, Garret has sent me rice photos of the Pandas in China during his visit to Shanghai, Chengdu, and Guangzhou (formerly Canton), a suburb of Hong Kong. He has given a presentation to Lab directors in China on behalf of his Company El Lill, Inc.

Mayte said that Jonathan Urbina's Wedding to Gabriza will be held this Saturday in Orlando: I guess the venue was changed from Miami. Jonathan comes from a big family (His Mom Raquel Hernandez), who I had the chance to meet some of them in Chicago. Judy, Marisol and Erika are in Orlando for the event. I know it will be Fun! Fun! Fun!

Mayte and I are watching Daniel for about eight days during this event He is attending 2nd Grade, I believe, at Colegio Rex- where Paul finished the 'Prepa'. We are also watching Judy's pitbull Maximo- he stays mostly in the back yard. At least our cats are cute survivors around the pitbull They love laying out in the sun on our ping pong table on the 2nd floor. Happy Campers!

Week Leading up to Jonathan Urbina's Wedding in Orlando
 March 14, 2024
 (13 of 20 Diary Entries)

So, this week we have been eating a better-than-usual diet of Hamburgers, Carne Azada tacos, Soya (Soy) Tecos, Banana Mik Shakes, Tomato soup and so on. I have been sharing 'dinner' with Nieve, Sabrina, Candy (sometimes) and Boni the dog. Nieve loves to jump on the Kitchen counter to get 1st dibs on the hot chow. Mayte says our neighbor Areceli's German Sheperd Merlina loves Maximo and they get along just fine. There is also word that Judy, Marisol & Erica (if I am not mistaken) are visiting Disney World in Orlando his very day. My son Paul has been to Disney Land in Anaheim back in 2012 with this Urbina group, and I have visited Sea World San Diego back in 1997 (with my friend Bill) when they still had the 'Shamu' Killer Whale show. Best Strawberry Cream Pie I ever had! ... In the French Styñe! Like NEIO alum Bob Bacchus once said in French, "Je suis le style!" which translates: 'I am the Style!'

Keep the Good Times Rolling!

Jonathan Urbina gets Married
 March 16, 2024
 (14 of 20 Diary Entries)

Jonathan Urbina got married to Gabriela today in Orlando, Florida, I am told by Mayte. It was going to be in Miami but the venue was changed. The Wedding photos were excellent. Mayte and Daniel went to Lomas and partied with one of Daniel's friends. The power in Sebastian Lerdo de Tejada went out and this probably had a direct impact on our current internet provider. The power was out here in Las Villas too from 2-5pm or so. The outages usually last a half-day or so. They happen dozens of times over the year. But at least Jonathan married Gabriela- makes one want to open a bottle of Champalgn-let the Good Times Roll!

Garret applies for German Citizenship
 April 5, 2024
 (15 of 20 Diary Entries)

I chatted with Garret online and he said recently his attorney, Charlotte Waning in Dusseldorf, Germany, had submitted his Application for German Citizenship to the Foreign Office. He said it may take months for him to get a receipt and that Applications can be in the pipeline for as long as three years before Citizenship is granted. At least when he gets it, he will be officially part of the 'German Diaspora.'

Also, Mayte is going with some friends out to the Sierra on Monday to see the total Solar Eclipse that will appear on April 8th, 2024. My son Paul is studying hard in Puebla and says he is graded on his projects, not exams. He went to one of the weekly festivals in nearby Cholula, which is known for its Great Pyramid.

Taking a Stroll & the Solar Eclipse

April 8, 2004

(16 of 20 Diary Entries)

I took a stroll into Sebastian Lerdo de Tejada (i.e. Lerdo) to buy a few snacks. I bought Maruchan Soup, Oreos, Pinguinos (cupcakes), Charros, & Chocolate Dots (not drugs). It was a very windy day.

Furthermore, Raymond Karlin contacted me from AHSGR and offered me Village Coordinator for three GR villages in Ukraine: Gnadental, Lichtental, and Sarata (not to be confused with Saratov). They are all located near Odesa, Ukraine. They were all Protestant and Mother Colonies. In addition, Sarata had a Jewish population. Initially, it appears, Sarata was a part of the Ottoman Empire, and when the Russian Empire expanded, it was absorbed by the Rusksies. Thereafter, German Settlers were invited in to help farm & populate Bessarabia. Gnadental and Lichtental are both mentioned in the wikipedia article on Sarata, which is the larger of the three. I was happy to accept Village Coordinator for all three towns.

The Solar Eclipse yesterday was amazing. They don't come around that often, that's for sure! At just after noon, the sky turned dark, as if a large cloud passed overhead. There seemed to still be light flowing from the 'side' of the sky. This lasted for about 20 minutes. I had to turn the lights on inside the house, because it appeared as if it was late evening. Then there was still less light for about 2-3 hours before it seemed like normal again, I took my daily walk in the afternoon and made sure not to look up-like something out of a Harrison Ford Movie!

All's well that ends well!

Brian & Mayte visit the Diabetic Clinic

April 10, 2024

(17 of 20 Diary Entries)

We visited the Diabetic Clinic today in the Zona Hospitales in Durango, Mexico, near lovely Parque Guadiana. We saw Dr. Arturo Flores Godines and he was cheerful as usual. My weight came in almost 90 kg, two higher than last time. They prescribed the usual meds, including insulin pens, but no Gabapantina was handed out which I definitely need. I did not have a lot of pain in my toes, which is good.

Afterwards, we went to Lomas and then Chedrauil, where I bought three Ensure shakes, some Sabritas chips, 2 taco bistec dinners, a pack of Parma Salchichas con Queso Cheddar y Jalapeño, Purina Fantastic Dell snacks for my cats, etc.; They were

filming a movie in the Barrio Tierra Blanca. Mayte put money in the bank to buy land- she wants to develop her real estate business.

After that, we went to Nogales where we met Martin, one of Mayte's workers. He had to do a job for Mayte, for her business. We noticed a brand new Mercedes-Benz near Mayte's home on Nogales. The home Mayte has there is very spacious. Then we bought construction material at Forrajes el Barrio a Ferreteria, along Central-East Durango. They sell big volumes, Then we picked up gas in Club Campstre at a Pemex there. Nice georgous Day in Mexico,

Thoughts about Religion

April 17, 2024

(18 of 20 Diary Entries)

When | was younger, always considered myself a Protestant, and nowadays I do as well, but 'would also say | am more of a 'Cultural' Christian', because I don't go to church alot anymore. When Mayte and I first came to Mexico, we visited Church a little bit, mostly for Midnight Mass at Christmas Time. The Catholic Churches are certainly among the most beautiful in the world. I have a deep respect for Religion. The funny thing about my 1st wife Ellen was she never talked much about Religion.

Recently I received word that Rose came down with Covid 19. But apparently she is feeling better because Mayte says Paul and her are taking jogs or runs together for exercise. He said it is hot in Puebla. It has certainly warmed up considerably here in Durango in the Spring- so much so that it is thoroughly enjoyable at night just to lay in bed comfortable as can be, with my cats practically snoring! Mayte has been fixing me rice and vegetables lately which is a nice change of pace from the usual snacks and I Have been nibbling on cinnamon too. Love her sunnyside eggs on tortillas in the mornings.

Purpose of this Diary

April 21, 2024

(19 of 20 Diary Entries)

I wrote this Diary to ensure that readers would get a glimpse of Brian Kaess' Life 'straight from the horse's mouth' so to speak. Yesterday, Mayte, Judy and Maribel left for Mazatlan, leaving me some roasted chicken and apples for snacks. They will be gone until Monday. They ae saying at the Mariott and Mayte says Judy is paying for everything. They normally stay at the El Pariaso in the 'Zona Dorado' or Golden Zone. When I was in Mazatlan in 2004, I remember walking from the 'Zona Dorado' to the old Historic City Center a couple of miles away just to mail a postcard.

Ours cats had a visitor last night, the nice male cat who comes to see them every now and then. Candy and Nieve both went outside in the front vard to mingle with him. He meows very gently and they coo back. It was like a season of cat love!

New Gadget
April 28, 2024
(20 of 20 Diary Entries)

We had the new Whirlpool Washing Machine delivered and Mayte has hooked it up nicely- it is really modern. It works like a Dream! She also had the 2010 Mitsubishi Outlander fixed (mucho pesos) and the wheels and tires needed to be changed, she said. Mayte said that last night (Saturday), her sisters Angelica, Judy and Marisol drank a lot of alcohol and got really drunk. She showed me video and they looked wild, spacy, and a bit tipsy. She also said that she sold a lot of stuff this morning at the Flea Market in Durango, including a children's bicycle. I was happy for her. Regina didn't go- she was tired.

The other day, Merlina, the neighbor's German Sheperd, aggressively chased our white cat Nieve (Mayte named her Nieve for 'Snow') right into the front door area, and I managed to ward her off while Nieve ran upstairs. Sabrina, our kitten, has also been known to fly onto me when she is scared of the neighborhood dogs, especially the German Sheperd.

Mayte also fed me some weak vegetable pies for dinner that weren't that tasty, but at least she cleaned up the storage room so it looks more like a computer room. In addition, I created an MS Access database to track sumames/villages in Upper Silesia that are relevant to my Polish family research.

Mayte's parents (Braulio & Maria Luisa) are in Arizona visiting David Urbina Sr., his girlfriend Abilena, and their daughter Abigail. Braulio was faint before he left and just wanted to lay down but they took him on the road anyway. Let's go 'old timer'! Mayte doesn't know the exact town they are staying, perhaps Chandler, Arizona, or Mesa, Arizona. Maria Luisa Pereda Guillon, Mayte's Mom, is undeniably the best cook in the family, and I am always a fan of her soups, Azada (spicy red pig meat) and rice, & noodles. Judy, my sister-in-law, has been known to cook up some mean came azada steaks with guacamole on floured tortillas. Mayte was really good at serving me up Ham & Cheese Quesadillas and salted Papas, but that era passed with the onset of the diet, to my eternal culinary regret. I myself have learned how to cook some mean, white, fluffy rice while living in Mexico.

Finally, | also contacted a 5th Cousin Angela Roberts who lives in Richmond, VA, -a descendant of the Eschenfelters. I chatted with her at virtual rootstech. Like the T-shirt says, "I'm a Cousin!"

Brian Kaess